

Influencing Factors of Academic Burnout and Coping Mechanisms of Student Leaders in BatStateU-Lemery and Balayan

Mhelett V. Atienza¹, Myke Chester M. Bathan², Marienel E. Manguerra³, Elaine Noreen G. Baxa⁴
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4042-3150>¹, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6546-6088>²,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5884-3591>³, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6052-5405>⁴
mhellet.atienza@g.batstate-u.edu.ph¹, mykechester.bathan@g.batstate-u.edu.ph²,
marienel.manguerra@g.batstate-u.edu.ph³, elainenoreen.baxa@g.batstate-u.edu.ph⁴
Batangas State University- Lemery Campus, Lemery, Batangas, Philippines¹⁻⁴

Abstract

Student leaders organize numerous activities that generate learning in support of strategic efforts and provide long-term programs that help to shape school policies. Consequently, it sometimes results in tiresome situations that could lead to academic burnout. With this, the researchers looked at the various factors that contribute to academic burnout of BatStateU Lemery and Balayan student leaders and their coping techniques. The study utilized a descriptive method and involved 98 student leaders. A research-based survey questionnaire was used as a data-gathering tool and employed percentage, chi-square, and Pearson r as statistical tools. Findings revealed that most of the student leaders of BatStateU Lemery and Balayan were 21-23 female 3rd year and linked with one organization. Academic burnout is prevalently influenced by emotional exhaustion specifically in terms of responding to urgent reports. Then, in depersonalization, burnout ignites when there was a lack of cooperation among others. Lastly, with reduced personal accomplishment, they struggled during unexpected outcomes out of the performance delivered. The majority looked at the positive aspects of the situations, calming down and recalibrating for improvement which fell under the problem-focused coping mechanism. More so it was found that there was no significant relationship between respondents' demographic profile and factors that influenced their academic burnout in reference to the three variables. However, emotion-focused coping had a significant relationship to emotional exhaustion while depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment had no significance. Activities proposed for student leaders to aid the influencing factors of academic burnout, practice proper coping mechanisms to create an engaging and positive nature of service.

Keywords: Student Leaders, Academic Burnout, Coping Mechanisms, Influencing factors, student organizations.

Introduction

Leadership is the ability to motivate a group of people to achieve a common goal. This is the chance to influence, inspire and assist others in becoming their best selves, while also developing their talents and attaining their objectives. Also, leadership is a set of abilities — as well as a mindset — that everyone can learn. Entering college organizations is a key developmental milestone, as well as opportunities to make new acquaintances, gain independence, experience, and improve a variety of skill sets. In BatStateU Lemery and Balayan Campus, student leaders actively engaged and created initiatives in forming impactful activities and projects for the benefit of the students. However, functioning as both student and a leader at the same time is a hard instance to handle, stressors arouse like time pressure, poor leadership styles, and negative behaviors of colleagues which could also fall to academic burnout.

In addition, student leaders have activities on a regular basis, which necessitates ongoing planning and organization in addition to self-efficacy, social involvement, and sound decision-making. Officers, on the other hand, may acquire burnout because of ongoing stressful situations. Burnout is a term coined by Fredenberger (1974) to

describe the emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment that can develop in persons who deal with them in some form. Researchers have been attempting to learn ways to overcome burnout to become psychologically robust people.

To address the determining elements of burnout, proper coping techniques must be considered. Role conflict or role overload, in which students struggle to comprehend their role and get stressed, are other causes of burnout. This is frequently seen in students starting new jobs, who are still learning what to do and what to anticipate from their new positions (Carruth, 2019).

However, because of this, many students spend a large portion of their non-academic time here fulfilling the duties of any leadership role they hold. Every semester, students attempt to strike a balance between their academic, professional, and personal obligations. When speaking with students, they often discuss their daily struggle to retain or even find this balance. Students organize campus-wide activities, contribute to long-term programs, and provide input that helps to shape university policy. To fulfill the demands of their leadership roles, students forego sleep, skip meals, and often neglect their academic obligations. Fear of a highly competitive job market, as well as a deep personal urge to help others, push students to take on more responsibilities than they can handle (Munasinghe, 2018).

Based on observations and experiences, continued burnout can lead to low self-confidence, depression, and a decrease in one's sense of personal achievement, which is not a positive sign of a student leader who is successful and productive. Furthermore, due to various roles, there have been instances of missed grades, inactive leadership, and mental breakdown. It exists when an individual uses the correct attitude and behaviors to protect themselves from the negative effects of a stressor. Individuals can prioritize more effective coping behaviors because of this.

This study was conducted to provide additional information about the factors that influence burnout and the coping strategies used when working responsibly on organizational activities and academic pursuits.

Objectives of the Study

This research study aimed to determine the influencing factors as sources of student leaders' academic burnout and the used coping mechanisms. Specifically, it sought to 1) determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, affiliated organization/s, year level, and campus, 2) identify the influencing factors encountered by student leaders as sources of academic burnout in reference to emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, reduced personal accomplishment, 3) discover how do student leaders cope up with the academic burnout in terms of problem-focused coping, emotion-focused coping, 4) distinguish if there is any significant relationship between the profile of the respondents to the influencing factors of academic burnout of the student leaders, 5) find out if there is any significant relationship between influencing factors and applied coping mechanisms of student leaders, 6) propose activities to reduce the impact of academic burnout and strengthen student leaders' coping mechanisms.

Methodology

The study used the descriptive research method and to satisfy the study's goals, probability sampling was utilized. This research was participated by organizational student leaders of two BatStateU's campuses: Lemery and Balayan whether appointed or elected. They were chosen because they had a higher risk of academic burnout while performing organizational activities and meeting academic criteria. As observed by the researchers, the higher the position of the officer the greater chances to encounter influencing factors of burnout.

The researchers selected 20 student leaders coming from the University Student Council, Teacher Education Student Council, and Association of Young Public Administrators BatStateU Pablo Borbon as respondents for the preliminary survey. The results passed the reliability, which proved that the questionnaire is accurate for the actual survey. After the pre-survey, the researchers humbly asked the permission of SOA Coordinators and Campus Directors of Campuses for the total number of student leaders enrolled from A.Y 2019-2021 through letters that were prepared by the researchers and noted by the thesis adviser and instructor. The researchers gathered a total population of 131, 84 student leaders from Lemery and 47 from Balayan. To come up with the sample size, the statistician suggested using Raosoft Calculator and Stratified Proportional or random sampling to compute the total number of respondents per campus to be used in the actual survey. It resulted in 98 target samples, 63 from Lemery, and the remaining 35 were representatives of Balayan.

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Questionnaires were made using Google forms and then sent to the concerned leaders. Organizations' Presidents helped a lot in reaching other members who belonged in the study. After receiving their responses, the researchers tabulated all the information. Afterward, the statistician guided the researchers; the data were analyzed through different statistical treatments including percentage, weighted mean, rank, Pearson's r, and chi-square.

Results and Discussion

This part exhibits the results, analysis, and interpretation of data based on the responses gathered from the respondents through questionnaires.

1. Profile of the Respondents

1.1. Age

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents in terms of Age

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
Below 18 yrs. old	0	0
18-20 yrs. old	34	34.7
21-23 yrs. old	51	52
24 yrs. old and above	13	13.3
Total	98	100

As seen in the table above, there were no respondents under the age of 18 who have been identified. However, there were 34 respondents aged 18-20, accounting for 35 percent of the total. There were 51 student representatives, or 52 percent, who were between the ages of 21 and 23. The remaining 13% went to 13- 24-year-old student leaders who took part in the data collection.

To sum up, most of the respondents of student leaders in BatStateU Lemery and Balayan belonged in the age bracket of 21-23. Oyoo (2018) conveys that those between the ages of 21 and 23 had a positive association with academic burnout. This meant that older students were more likely to experience academic burnout than younger students.

1.2. Gender

Table 3
Distribution of Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	41	41.8
Female	57	58.2
Total	98	100

The table illustrates the gender distribution of respondents. Females scored the highest frequency of responses, with 57 respondents, or 58 percent. The male party, on the other hand, is represented by 41 student leaders, who accounted for 42 percent of the total.

In brief, fair chances were given to males and females to serve however the data revealed that the majority of student leaders in BatStateU Lemery and Balayan were females because they were seen as committed and dedicated to fulfilling the task assigned. Its finding is in consonance with the study of Cymerman and Tomaszek (2020) where female students reported a higher emotional reaction to stressors, while male students reported higher behavioral and cognitive reactions to stressors. Women also scored significantly higher in emotional and avoidance coping styles as compared to men.

1.3. Affiliated Organization(s)

Table 4

Distribution of Respondents in terms of Number of Affiliated Organization(s)

Number of Affiliated Organization/s	Frequency	Percentage
1	90	91.8
2	4	4.1
3 and above	4	4.1
Total	98	100

Results show that 92 percent of the total population was linked with only one organization, with a frequency of 90 percent. Four student leaders were affiliated with two organizations and have gained four percent, which was comparable to the number of student leaders who were linked with three or more student groups on campus. It has been noted that the vast majority of student leaders of the BatStateU Lemery and Balayan dedicate themselves to a single organization to which they may devote their whole time and interest.

1.4. Year Level

Table 5

Distribution of Respondents in terms of Year Level

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
First Year	0	0
Second Year	18	18.4
Third Year	66	67.3
Fourth Year	14	14.3
Total	98	100

As a result of these findings, there were no documented first-year student leaders in the Balayan and Lemery campuses. Furthermore, the data showed that there were 18 second-year student leaders, accounting for 18 percent of the population. According to the poll, most officers in various student organizations were in their third year, with 67 percent. The rest 14 percent were the 14 fourth-year leaders who also participated in the study. So, most of the student leaders in BatStateU Lemery and Balayan were at the third-year level. Gomez et al., (2018) said that stress levels also differed by year, with first- and third-year students experiencing much less stress than second-year students. This could be due to second-year students' greater course loads and more challenging topics.

1.5. Campus

Table 6 features the distribution of respondents by campus. During the study, there were 63 participants from Lemery Campus, with a participation rate of 64 percent, and 35 from Balayan Campus, with a participation rate of 36 percent. When compared to the second campus, the first campus dominated data gathering due to the higher number of renewed organizations.

Table 6

Distribution of Respondents in terms of Campus

Campus	Frequency	Percentage
Lemery	63	64
Balayan	35	36
Total	98	100

2. Influencing Factors Encountered by Student Leaders as Sources of Academic Burnout

2.1. Emotional Exhaustion

Based on the results in terms of emotional exhaustion, responding to urgent reports scored the highest weighted mean of 3.20 and was interpreted as moderate extent. The respondents confess to feeling pressed by time and the potential consequences of their decisions. Baynton et al., (2016) said that stress, on the other hand, is normally perceived as feeling nervous and experiencing a sense of urgency, leading to burnout, which is more generally experienced as helplessness, hopelessness, or apathy. Participants may be unaware of the detrimental effects this can have on their performance, such as more errors or decreased productivity.

The researchers were student leaders who also experienced the same way. Responding to urgent reports in a short amount of time raises the likelihood of cramping, pressure, and stress, all of which contributed to burnout. In certain situations, the deadlines for the reports coincided with examinations and academic obligations. These factors were critical, which is why the officer had to battle and overcome exhaustion to meet the demands.

The results confirm that student leaders tend to be emotionally exhausted when they participated in untimely to meeting and forums, which obtained a 2.87 weighted mean and verbally interpreted as a moderate extent. Attending off-schedule meetings is linked to student leaders' emotional tiredness in a moderate way. Beqiri added that participating in meetings, pressure to perform to meet rising demands, meeting deadlines, fear of saying no, public speaking, and a loss of control about how to do the job were all common causes of workplace stress and anxiety.

2.2. Depersonalization

Assessment of the respondents on the factors as a source of academic burnout in terms of depersonalization has a 1.93 composite mean and verbal interpretation of slight extent. The highest rank factor is managed by lack of cooperation among student leaders scored a weighted mean of 2.32 and was verbally interpreted as a slight extent. Equally dividing this responsibility can mean recognizing when one needs to manage own feelings or step up to provide support to others. Student leaders on campus have remarked that there is still a lack of cooperation in student organizations. As a result, poor quality performance in relevant activities is the result. In certain ways, inappropriate behavior and attitude toward others were factors that influenced their poor participation.

Additionally, activities with inadequate support from top management and reduced production due to time constraints, both got a weighted mean of 2.05 with a verbal interpretation of slight extent. This indicates that the respondents were feeling burnt out when they cannot find enough support from administrators, which affects how they see themselves and results in a feeling of detachment. Other than that, time restrictions in handling tasks reduced the productivity of leaders, which may open to irritability and cramming.

Baynton et al. (2016) stressed that individuals may have greater instances of burnout when they feel that they were not making an adequate contribution to their organization, or do not feel their role conflict, work overload, even though they say they can handle it, or a lack of predictable and clear expectations are all factors to consider.

Performing tasks in the absence of recognition garnered a weighted mean of 2.01 and were verbally interpreted to a slight extent. Based on the responses of the respondents, giving recognition to the student leaders has less effect on their feeling of depersonalization. Murage et al., (2016) said that when leaders were not recognized then the following situations may arise. Academic life becomes very stressful since leadership roles, as well as personal studies, demand attention. These frustrations usually lead to students becoming more ungovernable and taking to the streets in demonstrations against the management of the university.

2.3. Reduced Personal Accomplishment

The results regarding the assessment of the respondents on factors as a source of academic burnout in terms of reduced personal accomplishment built a composite mean of 1.87, verbally interpreted as a slight extent.

The highest rank is to discern unexpected outcomes out of the performance delivered with a weighted mean of 1.98 and has a verbal interpretation of a slight extent. This proves that the respondents feel reduced personal achievement when they cannot meet the forecasted outcome due to the performance delivered.

Likewise, fails to meet the goal of the conducted activity gained a weighted mean of 1.96 and verbal interpretation of slight extent. It only pertained when student leaders failed to reach the expected result of the program or activity, as they experienced reduced personal accomplishment. The active role of students is very important in the context of forming a creative generation, which can produce something for the benefit of himself and others.

3. Coping Mechanisms of Student Leaders

3.1. Problem-focused coping

The assessment of the respondents on their coping mechanisms with academic burnout (problem-focused coping) had a 3.30 composite mean and moderate extent interpretation.

The statement looking at the positive aspects of the situation got the highest weighted mean of 3.58 and has a verbal interpretation to a great extent. The respondents showed that when one looks at the positive aspect of every situation, even if it is good, bad, or complicated, it says it is okay and it can lessen the worries.

Burnout has become reported as one of the impediments to student leaders' performance. Appropriate action and coping mechanisms must be added right away to avoid unproductivity. Watson clearly talked about practicing gratitude while looking at the positive aspects of the situation. Talk to closest friends, and support networks, about the things one is grateful for. Keep a gratitude diary to record feelings of gratitude for what one has daily. Even when unpleasant things happen, actively acknowledging what one is grateful for will help you maintain a thankful mind and heart. Burnout needs attention and calming down was found as one of the problem-focused coping being applied by the respondents with a weighted mean of 3.38 with a verbal interpretation of moderate extent. Calming down is a form of relaxation intended to relax the muscles in the body which is useful for reducing the tension felt by the body (Sari & Murtini, 2015). Diaphragmatic breathing might help relax the body during the study and all-day busy activities.

3.2. Emotion-focused Coping

These variable flashes the assessment practiced by the respondents to cope with academic burnout in terms of emotion-focused coping resulting in a total composite mean of 3.33 and a moderate extent verbal interpretation.

It can be noted that focusing on positive and personal growth gained the highest weighted mean of 3.55 and a verbal interpretation of a great extent. This item proved that the students could cope with academic burnout. The respondents claimed that for them to control their emotions and negative thoughts, they focused on the positive for personal development.

Adom et al. (2017) found out that managing academic stress is very effective when an individual activates a matured mindset by being optimistic against being pessimistic; this allows one to visualize stressors as opportunities for personal growth and development.

Student leaders may talk with people who demonstrate a positive outlook in life scored 3.51 total weighted mean to a great extent verbal interpretation. This means that student leaders can cope with academic burnout by communicating with people who have a positive mindset. In relation, Mansoor_et.al. said that students with positive personality traits like openness to experience, conscientiousness, extroversion, and agreeableness tend to perceive a lower level of academic stress. On the other hand, students with negative personality traits like neuroticism tend to perceive a higher level of academic stress.

4. Significant Relationship Between the Profile of Respondents to the Influencing Factors of Academic Burnout of Student Leaders

4.1. In terms Emotional Exhaustion

The relationship between respondents' profile and factors that influence their academic burnout when it comes to emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment.

Table 11

Relationship between the Respondents Profile and Factors that Influence their Academic Burnout (Emotional Exhaustion)

Profile variables	P-values	Computed values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Age	.439	5.863	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Gender	.533	2.193	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Number of affiliated organizations	.953	1.596	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Year level	.182	8.853	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

Table 11 presents the relationship between the respondents’ profiles and factors that influence their academic burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion. Since all the computed p-values were all higher than 0.05 level of significance, this indicates that there is no significant relationship between the profile of respondents and emotional exhaustion.

You et al., (2019) investigated the effects of gender, years of experience, and educational level on the presence of burnout dimensions. The findings demonstrate that all genders with Bachelors, Masters, and PhDs were experiencing emotional tiredness, regardless of years of experience. This indicated that diploma holders were not impaired by fatigue in the same way. This implies that teaching is a difficult occupation that necessitates emotional power. In relation, Oyoo (2019) revealed that there was an inverse significant correlation between academic burnout and academic achievement. More crucially, the study found that emotional exhaustion and cynicism had no bearing on academic performance. Meanwhile, Bikar et al. (2018) found that male students were more likely than female students to experience academic burnout. Michaeli et al. (2014) discovered that female students had better emotion management and positive affect than male students, as well as less academic burnout. However, there were no significant differences between these two groups when it came to negative affect and academic achievement.

4.2. In terms of Depersonalization

Table 12

Relationship between the Respondents Profile and Factors that Influence their Academic Burnout (Depersonalization)

Profile variables	P-values	Computed values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Age	.297	7.26	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Gender	.158	5.203	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Number of affiliated organizations	.871	2.478	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Year level	.898	2.224	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

The above table flashes the relationship between the respondents’ profile and factors that influence their academic burnout in terms of depersonalization.

Since all the computed p-values were all higher than 0.05 level of significance, this indicates that there is no significant relationship between the profile of respondents and depersonalization as factors of academic burnout.

De la Fuente et al. (2018) on the other hand, found a positive and statistically relevant connection between gender and depersonalization. Male nurses appeared to have a higher tendency to exhibit unfavorable attitudes toward patients and coworkers in the research that was included. This has an obvious impact on interpersonal relationships within the medical care team as well as interprofessional relationships between teams. It also has a negative effect on the service quality offered by the hospitals where these nurses operate.

4.3. In terms of Reduced Personal Accomplishment

Table 14

Relationship between the Respondents Profile and Factors that Influence their Academic Burnout (Reduced Personal Accomplishment)

Profile variables	P-values	Computed values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Age	.799	3.076	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Gender	.124	5.749	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Number of affiliated organizations	.817	2.934	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Year level	.833	2.802	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

Table 14 presents the relationship between the respondents' profile and factors that influence their academic burnout in terms of reduced personal accomplishment.

Since all the computed p-values were all higher than 0.05 level of significance, this indicates that there is no significant relationship between the profile of respondents and reduced personal accomplishment.

Stoliker and Lafreniere (2015) cited that a significant moment in a young adult's life can be marked by their time at the university, a time when university students can gain more independence, experience changes in social systems, gain important life skills, and of course, pursue a degree for a chance at a brighter future. Many students' university years can be pivotal moments in their lives; however, this time can also be a recipe for disaster due to the amount of stress and pressure college students endure with a college education.

Jamadulin et al. (2019) found that women with Master's degrees and six to ten years of experience had lower personal achievements. As a result, it can be deduced that the educators' lack of teaching effectiveness would result in a decline in their career success. This can be resolved if school officials and administrators have professional development opportunities for teachers and administrators. In relation, Heidari (2013) gender comparisons showed that female athletes experience higher levels of reduced sense of accomplishment. This evidence suggests that female athletes are more susceptible to burnout than male athletes. Two factors may contribute to these gender differences. First, female athletes, for starters, could be less capable of dealing with physical and mental strains. It must be noted that in the literature physical and mental stresses are considered the main factors in burnout. Second, the fact that female athletes had been less successful in international competitions may have led to feelings of failure, inefficacy, and reduced accomplishment. The disparity between expectations and outcomes is a major factor in the development of burnout.

5. Significant Relationship Between Influencing Factors and Applied Coping Mechanisms of Student Leaders

The association between the respondents' coping techniques and the factors that influence their academic burnout is shown in this table (problem-focused coping). The fact that all the computed p-values were more than 0.05 shows that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' academic burnout and the problem-solving approaches they used. It only applies to the fact that, no matter how tough it is to manage their burnout, they can still do their job tasks in the organization.

Shin (2014) conducted a meta-analysis to determine the relationship between the Emotional Exhaustion subscale of burnout and coping techniques. All coping factors (excluding reappraisal, acceptance, and religious coping techniques) revealed a considerable probability of variability among trials for emotional tiredness.

5.1. In terms of Problem-focused coping

Coping strategies are a resource that can have an impact on one's health and happiness. If participants had employed more problem-focused methods including planning, active coping, and instrumental support, they may have scored lower on both the emotional tiredness and depersonalization subscales of burnout (Stoeber & Jansse, 2011).

Table 15

Relationship Between the Respondents Coping Mechanisms and Factors that Influence their Academic Burnout (Problem-focused coping)

Factors	P-values	Computed r-values	Interpretation	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Emotional exhaustion	.215	.215	Weak positive relationship	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Depersonalization	.372	-.091	Very Weak negative relationship	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Reduced personal accomplishments	.212	-.127	Weak negative relationship	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

5.2. In terms of Emotion-focused coping

Table 16

Relationship between the Respondents Coping Mechanisms and Factors that Influence their Academic Burnout (Emotion-focused coping)

Factors	P-values	Computed r-values	Interpretation	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Emotional exhaustion	.02	.234	Weak positive relationship	Reject	Significant
Depersonalization	.838	-.021	Very Weak negative relationship	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Reduced personal accomplishments	.233	-.122	Weak negative relationship	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

This study backs up previous research by emphasizing the role of problem-focused coping mechanisms in treating burnout symptoms. Investing in more positive personal resources, such as problem-solving coping methods, can help relieve stress and reduce the risk of burnout. Table 16 exhibits the relationship between the respondents' coping mechanisms and factors that influence their academic burnout (emotion-focused coping).

Since the p-value of emotional exhaustion is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, then, it is significantly related to emotion-focused coping. Conversely, depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment were not found significant.

To put it another way, emotionally weary student leaders used emotion-focused coping to mitigate the negative impacts of burnout. The remaining contributing elements, such as depersonalization and reduced academic burnout, have a poor association with the coping method indicated because each student has their unique style of dealing with difficulties. Emotional weariness and depersonalization were found to be more strongly associated with emotion-focused coping in Shin's study.

It is worth noting the link between emotional weariness and the usage of emotion-focused coping. Reduced usage of emotion-focused coping mechanisms may result in lower levels of emotional weariness, which may help to relieve burnout (Isaksson Ro et. al. 2010).

6. Proposed Activities on Strengthening Student Leaders' Coping Mechanisms

Based on the findings had a chance to proposed student leader activities to strengthen their coping mechanisms. For Emotional Exhaustion the activity is Relax, I Got You!, second for Depersonalization, Best Fit Therapeutic Practices from Masters was planned, then lastly for the variable Reduced Personal Accomplishment, Gawad Student Leaders was on the list. These activities have their own unique objectives and success indicators.

Conclusion

The researchers were able to draw the following conclusions based on the study's objectives and primary findings. Most of the student leaders of BatStateU Lemery and Balayan as respondents belonged in the age bracket

of 21-23 This demonstrates that today's leadership is not solely for men, but also includes empowered women. Furthermore, more than half of the respondents are third-year students with prior experience organizing student events and programming and affiliated with one organization. Among other variables, it was found that emotional exhaustion mainly influenced leaders' academic burnout when they are tasked to respond to urgent reports. In depersonalization, also contributes to leaders' burnout when they manage a lack of cooperation among other student leaders. Lastly, reduced personal accomplishment placed the weakest influencing factors towards academic burnout. Leaders struggle when they discern unexpected outcomes out of the performance delivered. Problem-focused coping is the most common coping mechanism of student leaders in BatStateU-Lemery and Balayan to overcome burnout. They used to look at the positive aspects of the situation. When student leaders are categorized by profile, there is no substantial association between the determining elements of academic burnout. To address concerns about academic burnout, the study found that emotionally weary leaders were more likely to utilize emotional-focused coping, based on their significant relationships. Activities were suggested by the researchers for the student leaders to keep them engaged and enthusiastic while performing organizational chores.

Recommendation

The researchers crafted the following recommendations based on findings and conclusions: consultation with authorities for additional suggestions on how to improve the study's goal and action plan, solicitation of further need for compromise in the planned plan's line of action before its execution, and conduct a study-related study using various criteria for variables.

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